

#5: Societal and ecosystem consequences of climate tipping points

Climate tipping events can trigger widespread impacts on ecosystems, society, human health, and habitability. Impacts such as sea level rise, heat stress, drought, and water shortages may undermine food and water security, drive migration, and increase disease risks. Understanding these cascading effects requires assessing the multi-sectoral impacts of climate tipping points.

Action

TipESM will assess the impacts of climate tipping events on ecosystems and societies by developing and applying impact models to analyze multi-sectoral impacts and consequences for the UN Sustainable Development Goals. We will investigate the impact of ice sheet collapse on sea level and consequently, storm surges and coastal flooding in Northern Europe. We will also assess how climate tipping points may lead to changes in regional temperature, humidity and precipitation leading to abrupt changes in heat stress, wildfire, drought or flooding events. We will provide recommendations for acceptable heat stress limits as well as for extreme heat stress induced loss of habitability. TipESM will also investigate how tipping points affect the spread of infectious diseases and their vectors, focusing on malaria, diarrhoeal diseases, and zoonotic spillover.

By focusing on the impacts of climate tipping events on ecosystems and society, TipESM will:

- Assess the effects of abrupt sea level rise on storm surges and coastal flooding
- Investigate how tipping points in climate systems may affect temperature and humidity, and their impact on heat stress, fire, and drought
- Estimate the crossings of heat stress survivability limits and its impact on human displacement
- Quantify the effects of climate tipping on the distribution of infectious diseases and their vectors

The project

TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

Project partners and associated partners

- Danish Meteorological Institute
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (and their affiliated entities)
- The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
- University of Bergen
- The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
- Barcelona Institute for Global Health
- University of Leeds
- Met Office UK
- University of Reading
- University of Liverpool
- University of Bern
- Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research

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Project Coordinator:

Danish Meteorological Institute

Contact:

Dr Shuting Yang (sy@dm.dk)

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Understanding cascading risks of tipping points on ecosystems and society

TipESM will deliver new knowledge on the impacts of climate-tipping events on ecosystems and society in several areas. We will investigate the compound and cascading impacts on coastal regions resulting from abrupt ice sheet loss, sea level rise, and a potential increase in the likelihood and intensity of storm surges. We will assess how tipping-induced changes in temperature, humidity, and seasonality drive heat stress, wildfires, drought, and crop failure. Special attention will be given to moist heat waves, physiological heat limits, and urban–rural differences in vulnerability, to evaluate implications for human habitability and migration. TipESM will quantify how climate tipping alters the distribution of infectious diseases and the global range of vectors, focusing on malaria, diarrhoeal diseases, and zoonotic spillover. This includes tipping points altering the Sahel/West African monsoon, which may have a dramatic effect on malaria, and multiple Arctic ice tipping elements that may intensify diarrhoeal disease risks through shifts in the hydrological cycle. TipESM will further analyse how different tipping points may increase the risk of pathogen spillover due to dieback of the Amazon and African rainforests.

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TipESM - Exploring Tipping Points and Their Impacts Using Earth System Models

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Expected impacts of TipESM

The key objectives of the project are to:

- Advance knowledge and solutions in Earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, climate change adaptation, climate services, social science for climate action and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions
- Contribute substantially to key international assessments (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the European Environment Agency)
- Increase the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate and Earth system change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens
- Strengthen the European Research Area with increased knowledge of the risks of crossing climate tipping points

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